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2 **Transcriptomic Profiling Identifies Determinant Regulation for**
3 **Ammonium Tolerance in Wheat**

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PREPRINT

12 Abstract

13 Nitrogen is a crucial macronutrient for plant growth, supplied in agroecosystems primarily as
14 nitrate and ammonium. However, inefficient nitrogen use causes significant environmental
15 losses in wheat, where only 48% of applied nitrogen is converted into biomass, but stabilized
16 ammonium-based fertilization offers a promising strategy to reduce losses and enhance
17 sustainability. Ammonium nutrition can confer agronomic benefits, including improved grain
18 quality and stress tolerance in wheat, but high ammonium concentrations can be toxic,
19 impairing plant growth and triggering physiological and molecular defense responses. This study
20 aimed to investigate ammonium tolerance within a diverse panel of hexaploid winter wheat
21 (*Triticum aestivum* L.) accessions from the Gediflux collection. Hydroponic screening revealed
22 that while most wheat varieties preferred ammonium-nitrate, few genotypes exhibited superior
23 biomass production under ammonium-rich conditions. RNA-seq analysis of two contrasting
24 genotypes—one tolerant and one susceptible—uncovered distinct gene regulation patterns in
25 the tolerant cultivar. Notably, at the leaf level, genes encoding chlorophyll-binding proteins and
26 Rubisco were significantly upregulated, potentially enhancing photosynthetic capacity and
27 biomass yield. Additionally, key genes involved in abscisic acid signaling, including *PYL4*, *PYL5*,
28 and *PYL6*, were upregulated, suggesting a crucial role in chloroplast protection and stress
29 adaptation. To mitigate ammonium toxicity, the tolerant cultivar downregulated ammonium
30 transport and storage-related genes, such as *AMT2*, *CAP1*, and *TIP2;3*, indicating a controlled
31 ammonium homeostasis mechanism that limits excessive uptake and vacuolar sequestration.
32 In roots, auxin-responsive genes were predominantly upregulated in the tolerant cultivar, with
33 *ARF6*, *ARF10*, *ARF16*, and *ARF17* potentially contributing to root system reorganization for
34 improved ammonium tolerance. Ammonium nutrition significantly influenced transcriptional
35 regulation across roots and leaves, with the tolerant genotype exhibiting a stronger root
36 response and increased involvement in trichome morphogenesis, shoot development,
37 hormonal signaling, and stress adaptation. K-means clustering identified differentially

38 expressed transcription factors, including bZIP and WRKY-domain TFs associated with stress
39 signaling, as well as nitrogen metabolism-related TFs such as *ERF2* and *HRE1*. These findings
40 provide novel insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying ammonium tolerance in
41 wheat, highlighting potential targets for breeding varieties with enhanced nitrogen use efficiency
42 and stress resilience.

43 **Keywords**

44 Ammonium tolerance, bread wheat, transcriptomic profiling, transcription factors

45 **Introduction**

46 Within agroecosystems, inorganic nitrogen is supplied through fertilizers as nitrate (NO_3^-) and
47 ammonium (NH_4^+), essential precursors for amino acid biosynthesis and protein formation in
48 plants (Liu and von Wiren 2017). However, more than half of this nitrogen is lost to the
49 environment, leading to significant ecological concerns (Coskun et al., 2017). This inefficiency is
50 particularly evident in wheat, where only 48% of the applied nitrogen is converted into biomass
51 (Ladha et al., 2016). To address these losses, NH_4^+ -based fertilizers combined with nitrification
52 inhibitors have proven effective in reducing both nitrate leaching and greenhouse gas emissions
53 from nitrogen fertilization. By slowing the microbial conversion of NH_4^+ to NO_3^- , nitrification
54 inhibitors help retain nitrogen in a form less prone to leaching and denitrification (Beeckman et
55 al., 2024). Additionally, optimizing nitrogen use efficiency involves identifying plant varieties with
56 an enhanced capacity to assimilate NH_4^+ , further minimizing losses and improving
57 sustainability.

58 Sole NH_4^+ nutrition presents potential benefits for wheat production, including improved grain
59 quality and increased tolerance to salinity and cadmium stress (Ijato et al., 2020; Mousavi
60 Shalmani et al., 2023). This preference varies with environmental conditions, making NH_4^+ more
61 advantageous in certain situations, such as cold weather or rapid growth phases (Cramer et al,
62 1993; Mousavi Shalmani et al., 2017). However, the use of sole NH_4^+ nutrition remains debated

63 due to concerns about toxicity at high concentrations and plant's overall inclination toward NO_3^-
64 (Bittsánszky et al., 2015). Generally, while NH_4^+ is a crucial nitrogen source, its accumulation
65 can be harmful, with toxicity thresholds varying depending on species and overall concentration
66 (Britto & Kronzucker, 2002). Ammonium toxicity impairs root and shoot growth, induces leaf
67 chlorosis, and disrupts ionic balance, pH stability, and oxidative stress responses (Esteban et
68 al., 2016). The risk is particularly high when NH_4^+ is the only nitrogen source, especially in soils
69 with low nitrification rates or immediately after fertilization, where concentrations can reach up
70 to 40 mM (Britto & Kronzucker, 2002). Under these conditions, excessive NH_4^+ accumulation
71 significantly increases the likelihood of toxicity and its detrimental effects on plant
72 development.

73 At the cellular level, plants absorb NH_4^+ through high-affinity uptake transporters known as NH_4^+
74 transporters (AMTs) and assimilate it into amino acids via the glutamate synthase
75 (GS)/glutamine-2-oxoglutarate aminotransferase (GOGAT) cycle (Liu and von Wiren 2017).
76 However, excessive NH_4^+ accumulation can be toxic, prompting plants to activate various
77 protective mechanisms (Xiao et al., 2023). To mitigate NH_4^+ toxicity, plants regulate NH_4^+ uptake
78 by inhibiting AMTs (Straub et al., 2017), detoxify NH_4^+ -induced reactive oxygen species (ROS)
79 through antioxidant enzymes such as APX, CAT, and SOD (Xie et al., 2015), and maintain ionic
80 balance by increasing potassium levels to control NH_4^+ influx and efflux (Szczerba et al., 2008).
81 Additionally, NH_4^+ efflux is restricted through the action of VTC1, a GDP-mannose
82 pyrophosphorylase (GMPase) (Qin et al., 2008). Hormones also play a crucial role in NH_4^+
83 detoxification. At high NH_4^+ concentrations, abscisic acid (ABA) protects chloroplasts via the
84 metalloprotease AMOS1/EGY1 (Li et al. 2012) and limits NH_4^+ uptake by repressing AMTs
85 through the CIPK23 receptor in Arabidopsis (Ganz et al., 2022). In rice, ABA facilitates NH_4^+
86 detoxification by reducing ROS and free NH_4^+ levels through OsSAPK9 and OsbZIP20 (Sun et al,
87 2020). Auxin, in turn, helps maintain gravitropism at elevated NH_4^+ levels via the DnaJ-like
88 protein GSA1/ARG1 (Zou et al., 2013) and promotes NH_4^+ efflux in the root elongation zone

89 through the transcription factor WRKY46 (Di et al., 2021). Furthermore, brassinosteroids (BRs)
90 contribute to NH_4^+ tolerance by activating the auxin pathway in *Arabidopsis* following BR
91 treatment (Devi et al., 2022).

92 Plant species vary widely in their tolerance to NH_4^+ , with some displaying a preference for it
93 while others are highly sensitive. The response to NH_4^+ nutrition exists on a continuum, largely
94 depending on its concentration in the root medium. Certain species, like spinach, are extremely
95 sensitive to NH_4^+ (Lasa et al., 2022), whereas others, such as oil palm, are highly tolerant (De la
96 Peña et al., 2023). The highest NH_4^+ tolerance is typically found in plants adapted to low-
97 nitrification environments, such as conifers in acidic soils (Britto et al., 2013), and rice in oxygen-
98 limited paddy fields (Xiao et al., 2023). Additionally, intraspecific variation has been observed
99 within species like *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Sarasketa et al., 2014), pea (Cruz et al., 2011), rice (Di
100 et al., 2018), and the grass crop model *Brachypodium distachyon* (De la Peña et al., 2024),
101 suggesting that similar variability could also exist within wheat.

102 Wheat's tolerance to NH_4^+ remains largely unexplored, despite its importance in developing
103 varieties suited to more environmentally friendly fertilization strategies. This study aimed to
104 identify accessions with NH_4^+ tolerance within a set of hexaploid winter wheat (*Triticum*
105 *aestivum* L.) accessions from the Gediflux collection. Hydroponic screening revealed that only a
106 few varieties exhibited better leaf biomass in an NH_4^+ -rich medium compared to an NH_4NO_3
107 medium. RNA-seq analysis of two contrasting varieties for this trait led to the identification of
108 genes, including transcription factors, that help clarify the molecular mechanisms underlying
109 improved growth when NH_4^+ is at high concentration.

110 **Material and method**

111 Wheat material collection, hydroponic experiment and ammonium tolerance trait assessment

112 A collection of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) lines was established among the Gediflux
113 collection (Reeves et al., 2004), based on various geographical origins across Europe, including

114 genotypes obtained between 1945 and 2010. The collection also distinguishes genotypes
115 selected during or after the Green Revolution, comprising 110 genotypes (Figure S1). To assess
116 their performance in NH_4^+ tolerance trait, the genotypes were grown in a hydroponic system with
117 either NH_4^+ or NH_4NO_3 as the nitrogen source at a high level (10mM) of nitrogen. Fresh biomass
118 was measured for each genotype, and biomass ratios were calculated from three independent
119 experiments. Ratios greater than 1 indicate higher biomass production when grown with NH_4^+ ,
120 reflecting superior performance for the NH_4^+ tolerance trait. Confidence intervals between ratios
121 were computed using mratios package for R. Composition of the NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3 media were
122 the following: KH_2PO_3 (0.5 mM); MgSO_4 (1.00 mM), Fe EDTA (0.20 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), CaCl_2 (3.00 mM), KCl
123 (2,50 mM) for the macronutrients; H_3BO_3 (2.86 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), MnCl_2 (1.81 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), ZnSO_4 (0.22 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$),
124 CuSO_4 (0.051 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), Na_2MoO_4 (0.09 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) for the micronutrients. Nitrogen source were
125 brought either by $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (10.00 mM) and CaSO_4 (10.00 mM) or NH_4NO_3 (10.00 mM). The
126 genotypes were sown and pre-germinated in pots filled with sand, which was watered to its
127 maximum holding capacity. The pots were placed in a temperate growth room at 24°C with 16
128 hours light and 8 hours dark for six days. On the seventh day, the plants were transferred to
129 hydroponic systems. The plants were placed in two hydroponic tanks and aeration pump was
130 added to each tank. The final solution pH was adjusted to 7. The hydroponic system was kept in
131 a greenhouse for 13 days before harvesting. The temperature in the greenhouse was 22°C during
132 the day and 16°C at night with light intensity, between 100 and 120 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ from Lumigrow
133 pro 325 W LED light system (Lumigrow, Emeryville, CA, USA).

134 RNA extraction of wheat, library construction and sequencing

135 Four biological replicates of leaves and roots of wheat cultivars Cellule, showing a good
136 performance for NH_4^+ tolerance trait, and Pajero, bad performance, growing either on NH_4^+ or on
137 NH_4NO_3 hydroponic medium resulted in 32 samples. The samples have been reduced to powder
138 using liquid nitrogen, mortar and pestle, and then the extraction and purification of RNA of the

139 samples were performed using the NucleoSpin RNA Plant (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany),
140 following the manufacturer's instructions then stored at -80°C. RNA quality (RIN \geq 6.0,
141 28S/18S \geq 1.0) and quantity were checked using an Agilent 2100 bioanalyzer (Agilent
142 Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, United States) and Thermo Scientific™ NanoDrop™ One
143 Microvolume UV-Vis Spectrophotometers (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, United States). RNA
144 library construction and sequencing were performed by BGI Tech Solutions (Hong-Kong). Briefly,
145 mRNA was isolated from total RNA using oligo dT beads, then fragmented, and converted to
146 cDNA with N6 random primers. A second cDNA strand was synthesized with dUTP, marking it for
147 selective degradation. The double-stranded cDNA were end-repaired, adenylated at the 3' ends,
148 and ligated with adaptors. Uracil-DNA Glycosylase removed the dUTP-marked strand, leaving a
149 single strand that was PCR-amplified to create a sequencing-ready library. The amplified
150 product was then denatured by heat, cyclized using a splint oligo and DNA ligase and converted
151 into DNA nanoballs. The prepared DNA nanoballs were sequenced on the DNBSEQ (MGI Tech,
152 Shenzhen, China) platform.

153 Data filtering and mapping of reads

154 The sequencing data was filtered using SOAPnuke v1.5.6 by removing reads with sequencing
155 adapters, reads with more than 20% low-quality bases, and reads with over 5% unknown bases.
156 The remaining clean reads were saved in FASTQ format. The clean reads were mapped to the
157 *Triticum aestivum* cv. Chinese Spring IWGSC RefSeq v1.1 (Zhu et al., 2021) using HISAT2 v2.2.1
158 and Bowtie2 v2.4.4 was applied to align the clean reads to the gene set.

159 Differentially expressed genes (DEGs), GO enrichment, cluster and network construction

160 Expression level of gene was calculated by RSEM v1.2.28 to get read count, FPKM (Fragment per
161 kilobase of transcript per million reads mapped) and TPM (Transcript per million reads mapped).
162 Differential expression gene (DEG) analysis was performed using the DESeq2 with Q value
163 (corrected Pvalue) \leq 0.05. In this experiment, the gene expression comparison was performed

164 separately between two treatments (NH_4^+ vs. NH_4NO_3) and between two cultivars (Cellule vs.
165 Pajero) at the leaves and roots level. Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment was performed using Gene
166 Ontology database, then Phyper, a function of R v3.4.2 based on Hypergeometric test. The
167 significant levels of terms and pathways were corrected by Q value (corrected Pvalue) ≤ 0.05 .
168 The graphical representation of the cellular NH_4^+ transport and genes activation or repression in
169 Figure 3 was created using BioRender (<https://app.biorender.com/>). In this study, differentially
170 expressed transcription factors (DE-TFs) were obtained using “transcription molecular activity”
171 term of GO Molecular function, then a filter of $\text{TPM} > 0.05$ was applied. GO biological process of
172 the DE-TFs were obtained using Q value (corrected Pvalue) ≤ 0.05 . All alluvial diagrams were
173 made with RAWgraph (<https://app.rawgraphs.io/>). For the construction of clusters and
174 interaction network, amino acid sequences of the DE-TFs were first collected through BioMart
175 (<http://plants.ensembl.org/biomart>), then for each part (e.g. leaves and roots) interaction
176 network were built using STRING v12.0 (<https://string-db.org/>) based on k-means clustering
177 method, an unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for clustering data into distinct
178 groups. Visualization of the different DE-TFs clusters and interaction were made under
179 Cytoscape v3.10.3 (<https://cytoscape.org/>) by using the function “exportNetworkToCytoscape”.

180 **Results**

181 Phenotypic assessment of wheat genotypes in response to ammonium-rich environment

182 The selected panel consists of 110 winter wheat genotypes from northeastern Europe, including
183 local landraces and elite lines, to maximize genotypic variation (Figure S1). Trait performance is
184 based on the shoot biomass ratio (fresh weight) between plants growing on NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3 .
185 Values < 1 were considered as bad performers and > 1 as good (Figure 1a). Among the 110 tested
186 genotypes, only 5 exhibited higher fresh biomass in NH_4^+ medium compared to NH_4NO_3
187 medium. These genotypes, including Bledor, RUFUS, Folke, Starke II, and Cellule, were released
188 between 1950 and 2010 (Table S1).

189 Differential transcriptomic response between contrasting phenotypes for ammonium tolerance
190 trait

191 The analysis of transcriptional responses examined two genotypes with contrasting phenotypes
192 under high-dose NH_4^+ nutrition compared to NH_4NO_3 : Cellule, a high-performing genotype on
193 NH_4^+ , and Pajero, a low-performing genotype. The average alignment ratio of the samples to the
194 reference genome was 90.34%, and the average alignment of the gene set was 79.31% with a
195 total of 91,274 genes were detected. For each genotype and each plant part, leaves and roots,
196 between 2,800 and 3,600 genes were differentially expressed (DEGs) between NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3
197 conditions, except in the roots of Pajero, where only slightly over 1,000 genes were upregulated
198 (Figure 2a). Ammonium nutrition triggered the differential expression of 6.20% of total genes in
199 leaves and 5.64% in roots for Cellule, while in Pajero, 4.07% of total genes were differentially
200 expressed in leaves and 5.58% in roots. In both cultivars, the NH_4^+ signal induces DEGs with
201 motifs associated with perception (e.g., LRR, jacalin-like lectin) and transduction (e.g. kinase,
202 NB-ARC) (Figure S2a and Figure S2b). As shown in Figure 2b, in leaves, 1.29% of upregulated
203 genes (89 out of 6,893) and 15.74% of downregulated genes (911 out of 5,785) were common
204 between both genotypes. In roots, 39.42% of upregulated genes (1,684 out of 4,271) and 35.40%
205 of downregulated genes (1,587 out of 4,483) were shared between the two genotypes.
206 Interestingly, 372 out of 2,710 pfam-enriched up-regulated genes in Cellule and down-regulated
207 in Pajero were directly related to photosynthesis, including 103 genes encoding chlorophyll-
208 binding proteins and Rubisco (Figure S2a). Among them, 78 out of 135 were chlorophyll A-B
209 binding protein genes, while all 25 ribulose biphosphate carboxylase small chain genes and 24
210 ribulose-1,5-biphosphate carboxylase small subunit genes were upregulated. In Cellule, NH_4^+
211 triggered the expression of stress response markers in roots, including wound-induced genes,
212 chitinase-recognition genes, and chitinase (Figure S2b). Additionally, *ENOD93*, a gene known to
213 be associated with nitrogen fixation in legumes but conserved across the plant kingdom, was
214 upregulated in Cellule roots (Figure S2b). In contrast, NH_4^+ activated detoxification response

215 markers in Pajero, including peroxidases, dirigent-like proteins, cytochrome P450, and
216 glutathione S-transferases suggesting an increased requirement to manage NH_4^+ toxicity (Figure
217 S2f).

218 Identification of Differentially Expressed Genes Involved in the Ammonium and Hormonal
219 Pathways Contributing to Ammonium tolerance

220 A schematic representation of the tolerance observed in Cellule is shown in Figure 3 and a
221 detailed heat-map in Figure S4 and S5 for both genotypes. In Cellule, NH_4^+ transporters *AMT2*
222 and *AMT1;4* were significantly downregulated in both leaves and roots, whereas in Pajero, only a
223 single *AMT* gene was downregulated in leaves. In Cellule, *CIPK15* (CBL-interacting protein kinase
224 15) was overexpressed in roots, while in Pajero, *CIPK23* was upregulated in leaves. Notably,
225 *CIPK15* is known to suppress *AMT1* genes in Arabidopsis to mitigate NH_4^+ toxicity (Chen et al.,
226 2020). Increasing potassium levels is believed to regulate NH_4^+ influx and efflux by modulating
227 shared transport mechanisms and maintaining ion homeostasis (Szczerba et al., 2008). The
228 main difference in behavior between Cellule and Pajero was linked to the number of upregulated
229 and downregulated DEGs. While Cellule tends to reduce its potassium transport capacity—
230 evidenced by the majority of DEGs being downregulated in both leaves and roots—Pajero
231 exhibits a more balanced pattern, with an equal number of upregulated and downregulated
232 DEGs. In Cellule roots, *CAP1* and *TIP2;3* were significantly downregulated in roots. *CAP1*, a
233 tonoplast membrane malectin receptor, activates aquaporins *TIP2;1* and *TIP2;3*, which facilitate
234 NH_4^+ storage in vacuoles (Bai et al., 2014). Within the GS/GOGAT cycle, DEGs associated with
235 nitrate reductase (NR) were downregulated in both roots and leaves of Cellule, whereas were
236 upregulated in the leaves and downregulated in the roots of Pajero. Two DEGs associated with
237 glutamine synthetase (GS) are upregulated in Cellule, while only one is upregulated in Pajero. In
238 contrast, two DEGs associated with glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) are upregulated in the
239 leaves of Pajero, while only one is upregulated in Cellule. The *USUALLY MULTIPLE ACIDS MOVE*

240 *IN AND OUT TRANSPORTERS* (UMAMITs) family, specifically *UMAMIT14* and *UMAMIT19* and
241 *UMAMIT33*, has been previously identified as part of the NH_4^+ -specific transcriptome in
242 *Arabidopsis* (Patterson et al., 2010). In our dataset, only DEGs for *UMAMIT19* and *UMAMIT33*
243 orthologs were detected in both leaves and roots. In both cultivars, UMAMITs followed the
244 pattern: downregulated in leaves but upregulated in roots. In contrast, *TraesCS6A02G330100*,
245 which encodes UMAMIT19 in leaves, was overexpressed in Cellule but downregulated in Pajero.
246 Auxin-pathway response DEGs exhibited contrasting expression patterns between the two
247 genotypes, with Cellule showing a stronger auxin-driven activation, as 22 unique DEGs in leaves
248 and 16 in roots were and 16 in leaves and 11 in roots were downregulated. In Cellule, auxin-
249 related genes such as *ARF6* (Auxin Response Factor 6), *ARF17*, *IAA18* (indole-3-acetic acid
250 inducible 18), *IAA15*, *IAA26 (PAP1)*, *GH3.2* (Auxin-responsive GH3 family protein), *GH3.3* and
251 *GH3.4* were upregulated in leaves, while *ARF10*, *ARF16* *ARF17*, *ETT* (AUXIN RESPONSE
252 TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR 3), *GH3.2*, *GH3.4* and *GH3.3* in roots. Downregulated genes were
253 *GH3.2*, *GH3.3* and *GH3.4* in leaves and, *GH3.2*, *GH3.3*, *GH3.4*, and *GH3.5 (WES1)* in roots.
254 Additionally, *Small Auxin Up-Regulated RNA (SAUR)* genes, which are auxin-responsive but
255 whose functions remain unclear (Zhang et al., 2021), were predominantly upregulated in Cellule,
256 with *SAUR76* and *SAUR34* upregulated in leaves, and *SAUR71* upregulated in roots, whereas
257 Pajero showed downregulation of SAUR genes. In the abscisic acid (ABA)-activated signaling
258 pathway, Cellule exhibited the strongest ABA-pathway response with 15 unique upregulated
259 DEGs in both leaves and roots while 5 in leaves and 15 in roots downregulated DEGs. The
260 upregulated DEGS were *PYL4* (pyrabactin resistance 1-like 4), *PYL5*, *PY6*, *EHB1* (ENHANCED
261 BENDING 1), *C2* (CaLB domain family protein), *BETA-OHASE 1* (beta-hydroxylase 1), *BETA-*
262 *OHASE 2*, *HHP1* (heptahelical transmembrane protein1), *AO1* (aldehyde oxidase 1), *AAO2*,
263 *AAO3*, and *AO4* in leaves and *AREB3* (ABA-responsive element binding protein 3), *EEL*
264 (ATBZIP12), *SDR2* (NAD(P)-binding Rossmann-fold superfamily protein), *NCED2* (nine-cis-
265 epoxy-carotenoid dioxygenase 2), *NCED3*, *NCED5*, *NCED9*, *AO1*, *AAO2*, *AAO3*, *AO4*, and *KOB1*

266 (ABA INSENSITIVE 8) in roots. The downregulated DEGs were only *BETA-OHASE 1*, *BETA-OHASE*
267 *2*, *SDR2*, *AO1*, *AO4*, and *AAO3* in roots. In the brassinosteroid-mediated signaling pathway, only
268 a few DEGs were identified. In leaves, Cellule exhibited upregulation of *BR6OX1*
269 (brassinosteroid-6-oxidase 1), *BR6OX2*, *BSK3* (brassinosteroid-signaling kinase 3) *BSK4* and, and
270 in roots, *BR6OX1*, *BR6OX2*, *BSK4*, *BSK3* and *ASP1* (aspartate aminotransferase 1).
271 Downregulated DEGs were in leaves *BR6OX1* and *BR6OX2* in leaves and *BR6OX1*, *BR6OX2*,
272 *BSK1*, *KAO2* (ent-kaurenoic acid hydroxylase 2), *CYP88A3* (ENT-KAURENOIC ACID OXYDASE 1)
273 and *CYP708A1*.

274 Transcription Factors Driving Ammonium Tolerance Across Contrasting Genotypes

275 A total of 168 differentially expressed transcription factors (DE-TFs) with a Log_2 fold change > 1
276 were observed in the leaves of Cellule, compared to 126 in the roots. In Pajero, 151 DE-TFs were
277 detected in the leaves and 134 in the roots. Overall, Cellule exhibited a higher number of DE-TFs
278 than Pajero, with a notably greater proportion of DE-TFs showing a Log_2 fold change between 2
279 and 5 (Figure 4a). Among these DE-TFs, 104 in the leaves and 97 in the roots of Cellule, as well
280 as 63 in the leaves and 94 in the roots of Pajero, were assigned GO P terms and are presented in
281 Figure 4b. In the leaves, transcriptional activity regulation is a common process between the two
282 genotypes and represents the majority of the identified terms (66.34% in Cellule and 85.57% in
283 Pajero). A similar trend is observed in the roots, accounting for 75.25% in Cellule and 80.85% in
284 Pajero. Some DE-TFs are also associated with salicylic acid and adventitious root development
285 in both genotypes. In Cellule, the leaf response is characterized by DE-TFs related to leaf
286 development, such as trichome morphogenesis, the regulation of shoot system development,
287 and phosphorous regulation, including phosphate ion homeostasis and positive regulation of
288 cellular response to phosphate starvation and hormones (jasmonic acid and gibberellins).
289 Additionally, 10 DE-TFs are associated with the cellular response to heat, including orthologs of
290 heat shock transcription factors found in Arabidopsis. In Pajero, DE-TFs are notably associated

291 with regulation of secondary shoot formation and nuclear envelope organization. In the roots,
292 Cellule is distinguished by DE-TFs related to root development, particularly anatomical
293 structure development, while Pajero shows associations with phosphorous regulation, such as
294 positive regulation of cellular response to phosphate starvation and cell cycle regulation.
295 Clusters of DE-TFs were established based on genes previously enriched using the k-means
296 clustering method. A total of nine clusters were identified in leaves and seven in roots (Table 1).
297 In both leaves and roots, cluster 1 contains the highest number of genes, with the most diverse
298 protein descriptions. Remarkably, 13 DE-TFs are shared between these two cluster 1 groups,
299 suggesting a common regulation mechanism. The association network between the DE-TFs of
300 cluster 1 is represented in Figure 4c in leaves and in roots. The confidence score of the predicted
301 associations between DE-TFs ranges from 0.40 to 0.96 in leaves and from 0.41 to 0.96 in roots.
302 Among TFs involved in plant biotic and abiotic stress responses, we identified bZIP-motif TFs
303 and form the highest number of associations (8–10 connections), including the *bZIP49* ortholog
304 (*TraesCS2B02G167900*), which interacts with *bZIP25* (*TraesCS5A02G057500*) and *bZO2H1*
305 (*TraesCS5D02G068800*) with a confidence score of 0.944 for both interactions. Additionally, we
306 identified WRKY-motif TFs, including wheat orthologs of *WRKY50* (*TraesCS3B02G240200*,
307 *TraesCS3D02G212700*), *WRKY55* (*TraesCS1B02G243100*, *TraesCS6A02G080500*,
308 *TraesCS6B02G108000*), and *WRKY46* (*TraesCS2B02G187500*, *TraesCS3D02G238300*,
309 *TraesCS7B02G012600*). Particularly, Arabidopsis *WRKY46* had been previously reported as a key
310 regulator of NH_4^+ tolerance (Di et al., 2021). Additional TFs of the cluster 1 linked to nitrogen
311 metabolism are shown in Table 2.

312 Discussion

313 Transcriptional Adaptation in Response to an Ammonium-Rich Nutritional Environment

314 In general, wheat shoot and root biomass are significantly higher under NH_4NO_3 treatment
315 compared to pure NH_4^+ (Chen et al., 2024). Based on shoot biomass, our results indicate that

316 the vast majority of wheat genotypes in the collection exhibit a preference for NH_4NO_3 . However,
317 five genotypes consistently preferred NH_4^+ across three independent experiments. Similar to
318 findings in *Arabidopsis* (Sarasketa et al., 2014) and *Brachypodium* (De la Peña et al., 2024), our
319 study highlights intraspecific variability in NH_4^+ tolerance within wheat, demonstrating diverse
320 adaptive responses to nitrogen sources. Within two contrasting wheat genotypes for NH_4^+
321 tolerance, Cellule (tolerant) and Pajero (susceptible), we observed that NH_4^+ signaling triggered
322 DEGs motifs associated with perception (e.g., LRR, jacalin-like lectin) and transduction (e.g.,
323 kinase, NB-ARC) in both genotypes. These motifs, typically found in membrane receptors, may
324 play a role in membrane and cell wall reorganization, as well as exocytosis, as suggested by GO
325 cellular enrichment analysis (Figure S3a and Figure S3b). Additionally, as illustrated in the Venn
326 diagram (Figure 2b), Cellule exhibited a more specific functional response in leaves than in
327 roots. In leaves of Cellule, the upregulation of pfam-enriched and GO cellular-enriched genes
328 was directly related to photosynthesis, suggesting that NH_4^+ nutrition enhances Cellule's
329 photosynthetic capacity and potentially contributes to its higher biomass yield. In roots, GO
330 cellular enrichment analysis revealed that NH_4^+ triggered the expression of stress response
331 markers in Cellule, whereas Pajero exhibited a stronger detoxification response. Interestingly,
332 *ENOD93* was upregulated in Cellule: studies in rice have identified *ENOD93* as an N-responsive
333 gene, and its overexpression in transgenic rice lines has been shown to enhance nitrogen use
334 efficiency (Bi et al., 2009). In the NH_4^+ assimilation pathway, the downregulation of *AMT2* in both
335 leaves and roots of Cellule suggests a moderated regulation of NH_4^+ uptake. *AMT2* plays a
336 crucial role in facilitating NH_4^+ movement between the apoplast and symplast across plant cells
337 (Sohlenkamp et al., 2002). This downregulation may contribute to NH_4^+ tolerance in Cellule by
338 limiting excessive extracellular NH_4^+ uptake and restricting its internal transport, thereby
339 reducing potential toxicity. Additionally, the downregulation of *CAP1* and *TIP2;3* in Cellule roots
340 indicates a reduced tendency for NH_4^+ storage in vacuoles, further suggesting a controlled NH_4^+
341 homeostasis strategy. In contrast, Pajero exhibits a distinct response, as indicated by the

342 upregulation of multiple potassium transport-related DEGs in both leaves and roots. This
343 suggests a more active potassium transport system, which likely serves as a protective
344 mechanism to counteract NH_4^+ toxicity by maintaining ionic balance and reducing NH_4^+ stress
345 (Szczerba et al., 2008). Excess NH_4^+ inhibits plant growth; however, glutamine synthetase (GS)
346 plays a crucial role in mitigating its toxicity by assimilating NH_4^+ into organic compounds (Leng
347 et al., 2024). In Cellule roots, we identified two upregulated DEGs encoding GS, which may
348 contribute to enhanced NH_4^+ detoxification and improved tolerance in this genotype.
349 Interestingly, the large majority of DEGs related to auxin-responsive were found in Cellule leaves
350 and roots, and most of them were upregulated. Among these, members of the Auxin Response
351 Factor (ARF) family were identified, *ARFs* are key regulators of auxin signaling, modulating the
352 expression of early auxin-responsive genes such as *Aux/IAA*, *GH3*, and *SAUR*, and thereby
353 regulating downstream signaling pathways (Abel and Theologis, 1996). In leaves, wheat ortholog
354 of *ARF6* was found, previous studies showed that *OsARF6* regulates flag-leaf angles (Chen et al.,
355 2018) and influences tiller number (Liu et al., 2012). In roots, *ARF10*, *ARF16*, and *ARF17* were
356 identified; other research indicated that *AtARF10* controls root cap cell formation (Wang et al.,
357 2005), *OsARF16* inhibits primary root length and lateral root formation (Shen et al., 2013), and
358 *AtARF17* plays a crucial role in adventitious root formation (Gutierrez et al., 2009). These findings
359 suggest that the reorganization of the root system may be critical for NH_4^+ tolerance. Among the
360 ABA-responsive DEGs, Cellule upregulates members of the pyrabactin resistance 1-like (*PYL*)
361 family in leaves, including *PYL4*, *PYL5*, and *PYL6*, which are ABA perception receptors (Dupeux et
362 al., 2011). These receptors are expressed in response to various stresses, including drought,
363 heat, and salt stress. Notably, *OsPYL6* exhibited the highest expression levels across all tissues
364 and under different abiotic stresses (Yadav et al., 2020). ABA signaling plays a crucial role in
365 regulating the expression of NH_4^+ -responsive genes that help maintain chloroplast integrity in
366 the presence of high NH_4^+ levels (Li et al., 2012), and enhanced perception in Cellule may
367 facilitate this process.

368 Transcription Factors Driving Ammonium Tolerance Across Contrasting Genotypes

369 The transcriptional response of plants to environments where NH_4^+ is the sole nitrogen source
370 has been previously studied in *Arabidopsis* and described as distinct from the NO_3^- response
371 (Patterson et al., 2010). However, the transcriptional response to high NH_4^+ concentrations
372 remains unexplored, particularly in wheat. Identifying TFs involved in mitigating NH_4^+ toxicity at
373 elevated concentrations is therefore crucial. Our study focused on the identification and
374 characterization of TFs in two wheat genotypes with contrasting tolerance to NH_4^+ . To isolate
375 these TFs, we selected those whose expression significantly differed between NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3
376 conditions in both genotypes. Cellule exhibited a higher number of differentially expressed TFs
377 than Pajero, particularly in leaves, with a \log_2 fold change between 2 and 5. Under NH_4^+ nutrition,
378 transcriptional regulation emerged as the most TF-enriched biological process in both
379 genotypes, in both root and leaf tissues. In addition, NH_4^+ signal induced TFs associated with
380 morphological reorganization of the shoot system in both genotypes, while Cellule exhibited a
381 stronger root response. However, the nature of this morphological adaptation differed: Cellule
382 displayed a greater involvement of TFs related to trichome morphogenesis, regulation of shoot
383 system development, and a higher dependence on jasmonic acid and gibberellin signaling.
384 Additionally, Cellule showed a strong induction of TFs related to cellular response to heat in
385 leaves, suggesting a heightened ability to mobilize a transcriptomic response to stress. Notably,
386 TFs regulating phosphorus homeostasis also appeared to contribute to Cellule's response to
387 NH_4^+ signal. Furthermore, a k-means clustering analysis based on TF interactions identified
388 foliar cluster 1 and root cluster 1 with 13 common DE-TFs in both leaves and roots. At the core of
389 these interactions were three bZIP-domain TFs: the orthologs *bZIP49*, *bZIP25*, and *BZO2H1*. In
390 plants, bZIP TFs are well-documented for their roles in both biotic and abiotic stress responses,
391 including pathogen defense and stress signaling. However, like many TF families, their functions
392 often overlap, adding complexity to their analysis (Jakoby et al., 2002). Patterson et al. (2010)
393 previously identified WRKY-domain TFs in the NH_4^+ -responsive transcriptome of *Arabidopsis*,

394 including *WRKY33*, *WRKY40*, *WRKY53*, and *WRKY70*. These TFs, already known for their roles in
395 pathogen defense regulation, were also upregulated by NH_4^+ , serving as markers of this nitrogen
396 nutrition pathway. In our study, within cluster 1, we identified the differential expression of the
397 wheat orthologs of *WRKY50*, *WRKY55*, and *WRKY46*, which may represent specific markers of
398 the transcriptional response to high NH_4^+ concentrations. Particularly, orthologs of Arabidopsis
399 *WRKY46*, were detected in the leaf cluster 1 and had been previously reported as a key regulator
400 of NH_4^+ tolerance (Di et al., 2021). This gene binds to the promoters of *NUDX9* and *IAA-*
401 *conjugating* genes, repressing their transcription and ultimately inhibiting NH_4^+ efflux in the
402 elongation zone. Furthermore, several DE-TFs in cluster 1 are directly linked to the study by
403 Gaudinier et al. (2018), which identified transcription factors (TFs) in Arabidopsis that regulate
404 nitrogen metabolism. Within this cluster, we identified 12 DE-TFs in leaves and 12 in roots. Most
405 of the selected TFs were found to target a single promoter gene, with the notable exception of
406 *ERF2*. This TF, detected in wheat leaves, targeted seven promoters, including *GLN1;2* (glutamine
407 synthetase 1;2), *GLT1* (NADH-dependent glutamate synthase 1), and *GLN1;3* (glutamine
408 synthetase 1;3).

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414 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

415 AB and HV conceived the original idea. AB wrote the manuscript. AB, IJ and YM carried out the
416 experiments. AB and IJ carried out data processing. FH and HV fundings.

417 **Declaration of competing interest**

418 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could
419 be perceived as influencing the research presented in this paper.

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424 **Data availability**

425 The datasets supporting this article are available in the SRA data number PRJNA1238568.

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573

PREPRINT

a)

b)

575 **Figure 1:** Identification of wheat cultivars within the Gediflux panel for ammonium tolerance
576 trait. A, Trait performance is based on the shoot biomass (fresh weight) ratio between plants
577 growing on NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3 . Values <1 were considered as bad performers and >1 as good.
578 The assessment consists of three independent experiments represented by either a green
579 square, a blue triangle or a red round. Cultivar number (cv. Number) and associated genotype
580 name are detailed in Table S1. B, Photo of hydroponic systems.

581

PREPRINT

583 **Figure 2:** Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) between two contrasted wheat cultivars for
584 ammonium tolerance trait (Cellule, good performer; and Pajero, bad performer). A, Number of
585 genes differentially expressed between NH_4^+ and NH_4NO_3 in each wheat cultivar in leaves and
586 roots; red bar: up-regulated and blue bar: down-regulated. B, Venn diagrams depicting the
587 overlap between up- and down-regulated genes in the two contrasted cultivars, in leaves and
588 roots.

589

PREPRINT

591 **Figure 3:** Schematic representation of ammonium transport at the cellular level in roots and leaf
592 compartments of the high-performing variety (Cellule). The diagram highlights the activation and
593 repression of genes associated with the ammonium pathway, including the GS/GOGAT cycle, as
594 well as genes from related hormonal pathways (ABA, and Aux).

595

PRE PRINT

a)

b)

c)

597 **Figure 4:** Differentially expressed transcription factors (DE-TFs) between two contrasting wheat
598 cultivars for ammonium tolerance. A, Number of DE-TFs categorized by expression levels: dark
599 green bar – Cellule leaves, light green bar – Pajero leaves, brown bar – Cellule roots, orange bar –
600 Pajero roots. B, Alluvial diagrams showing Gene Ontology (GO) biological process enrichments
601 for all DE-TFs with Q-value ≤ 0.05 in leaves (left) and roots (right); the height of the bars is
602 proportional to the number of genes. C, DE-TFs interactions in cluster 1 of leaves (left) and
603 cluster 1 of roots (right), based on STRING analysis. The edge color indicates the confident score
604 of the predicted association between DE-TFs from the STRING analysis, ranging from blue for a
605 weak confidence to red for a strong confidence.

606

PREPRINT

607 **Table 1:** Clustering of DE-TFs using the k-means method. For each part (leaves and roots), the
 608 number of genes per cluster and the corresponding protein descriptions are provided.

	Cluster number	Gene count	Protein description
Leaves	1	44	AP2/ERF domain-containing protein. BHLH domain-containing protein. BZIP domain-containing protein. C2H2-type domain-containing protein. Ethylene response factor. HDAC_interact domain-containing protein. HSF_DOMAIN domain-containing protein. HTH cro/C1-type domain-containing protein. NAD(P)-bd_dom domain-containing protein. Q-type C2H2 zinc finger protein. RNA polymerase sigma factor; Sigma factors are initiation factors that promote the attachment of plastid-encoded RNA polymerase (PEP) to specific initiation sites and are then released. Transcription initiation factor IIF subunit alpha; TFIIF is a general transcription initiation factor that binds to RNA polymerase II and helps to recruit it to the initiation complex in collaboration with TFIIB. It promotes transcription elongation. Belongs to the TFIIF alpha subunit family. Uncharacterized protein. WRKY domain-containing protein. WRKY transcription factor WRKY1A. WRKY49 transcriptional factor.
	2	7	WRKY domain-containing protein.
	3	4	CBFD_NFYB_HMF domain-containing protein.
	4	3	WRKY domain-containing protein.
	5	3	WRKY domain-containing protein.
	6	3	ASCH domain-containing protein. Uncharacterized protein.
	7	2	Heat shock transcription factor. Homeobox domain-containing protein.
	8	2	BHLH27. BZIP domain-containing protein.
	9	2	Two-component response regulator; Transcriptional activator that binds specific DNA sequence.
	Roots	1	42

Ethylene response factor.
 Heat shock factor C2a.
 HSF_DOMAIN domain-containing protein.
 MIKC-type MADS-box transcription factor WM13.
 PWWP domain-containing protein.
 Q-type C2H2 zinc finger protein.
 TAZ-type domain-containing protein.
 Transcription initiation factor IIF subunit alpha; TFIIF is a general transcription initiation factor that binds to RNA polymerase II and helps to recruit it to the initiation complex in collaboration with TFIIB. It promotes transcription elongation. Belongs to the TFIIF alpha subunit family.
 Uncharacterized protein.
 Uncharacterized protein; Belongs to the PI3/PI4-kinase family.

2	14	Uncharacterized protein. WRKY domain-containing protein.
3	5	BZIP domain-containing protein. WRKY domain-containing protein.
4	3	Homeobox domain-containing protein. Uncharacterized protein.
5	3	AP2/ERF domain-containing protein. BHLH domain-containing protein.
6	3	CBFD_NFYB_HMF domain-containing protein. Uncharacterized protein.
7	2	Homeobox domain-containing protein.

610 **Table 2:** Transcription factors of the cluster 1 associated to nitrogen metabolism

Wheat TF	Arabidopsis ortholog TF	Arabidopsis gene targets	Reference
<i>TraesCS7A02G160700</i>	STZ (salt tolerance zinc finger)	AFB2 (auxin signaling F-box 2)	
<i>TraesCS5A02G314600</i>	HRE1 (Integrase-type DNA-binding superfamily protein)	NIR1 (nitrite reductase 1)	
<i>TraesCS5B02G315500</i>			
<i>TraesCS5D02G320800</i>			
<i>TraesCS2A02G417300</i>	ERF2 (ethylene-responsive element binding factor 2)	GLN1;2 (glutamine synthetase 1;2), GLT1 (NADH-dependent glutamate synthase 1), and GLN1;3 (glutamine synthetase 1;3), GLT1 (NADH-dependent glutamate synthase 1), MDH (malate dehydrogenase), PGI1 (phosphoglucose isomerase 1), ANR1 (AGAMOUS-like 44), DREB26 (Integrase-type DNA-binding superfamily protein)	Gaudinier et al. 2018
<i>TraesCS2B02G436300</i>			
<i>TraesCS2D02G414600</i>			
<i>TraesCS2A02G417300</i>	RAP2.12 (uncharacterized protein)	GDH2 (glutamate dehydrogenase 2), MDH (malate dehydrogenase), ALAAT2 (alanine aminotransferase 2)	
<i>TraesCS4B02G079000</i>	AZF2 (zinc-finger protein)	ALAAT2 (alanine aminotransferase 2)	
<i>TraesCS5A02G070600</i>		CNX2 (cofactor of nitrate reductase and xanthine dehydrogenase 2)	
<i>TraesCS5B02G076400</i>			
<i>TraesCS5D02G082700</i>			

TraesCS5A02G070600

TraesCS5B02G076400

TraesCS5D02G082700

TraesCS7A02G160700 AZF3 (zinc-finger ALAAT2 (alanine aminotransferase 2)

TraesCS7A02G160700 protein)

TraesCS6A02G080500 WRKY 55 (DNA-binding XERICO (RING/U-box superfamily

TraesCS6B02G108000 protein 55) protein)

TraesCS1B02G243100

TraesCS3B02G476000 SCRM2 (basic helix- SLR (indole-3-acetic acid inducible

TraesCS3B02G476000 loop-helix (bHLH) DNA- 14)

binding superfamily

protein)

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615 **Figure S1:** Geographical origins of bread wheat genotypes used from the Gediflux panel,
616 distribution of genotypes by decade since 1940, and classification based on the Green
617 Revolution.

618

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620 **Figure S2:** Enrichment bubble chart for Pfam annotation enrichment for DEGs in Cellule and
621 Pajero genotypes at the leaf and root levels. A, Up- and down- regulated for both genotypes in
622 leaves. B, Up- and down- regulated for both genotypes in roots. C, Up-regulated for Cellule or
623 down-regulated for Pajero in leaves. D, Up-regulated for Cellule or down-regulated for Pajero in
624 roots. E, Up-regulated for Pajero or down-regulated for Cellule in leaves. F, Up-regulated for
625 Pajero or down-regulated for Cellule in roots. Annotations with Q-value ≤ 0.05 are considered
626 significantly enriched.

627

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629 **Figure S3:** Enrichment bubble chart for Gene Ontology (GO) Cellular enrichment for DEGs in
630 Cellule and Pajero genotypes at the leaf and root levels. A, Up- and down-regulated for both
631 genotypes in leaves. B, Up- and down-regulated for both genotypes in roots. C, Up-regulated for
632 Cellule or down-regulated for Pajero in leaves. D, Up-regulated for Cellule or down-regulated for
633 Pajero in roots. E, Up-regulated for Pajero or down-regulated for Cellule in leaves. F, Up-
634 regulated for Pajero or down-regulated for Cellule in roots. Annotations with Q-value ≤ 0.05 are
635 considered significantly enriched.

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637

a) Ammonium transporters and storage

b) Potassium transporters

c) GS/GOGAT cycle

d) UMAMITs

638 **Figure S4:** Heatmap representing DEGs associated with the ammonium pathway in Cellule and
639 Pajero genotypes, at the leaf and root levels. A, Ammonium transporters and regulators, and
640 vacuolar storage. B, Potassium transporters. C, GS/GOGAT cycle enzymes. D, UMAMIT19 and
641 UMAMIT33 transporters.

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a) ABA signaling pathway

b) Auxin signaling pathway

c) BR signaling pathway

644 **Figure S5:** Heatmap representing DEGs associated with hormonal pathways in Cellule and
 645 Pajero genotypes, at the leaf and root levels. A, Auxin signaling pathway. B, Abscisic acid (ABA)
 646 signaling pathway. C, Brassinosteroid (BR) signaling pathway.

647 **Table S1:** List of bread wheat genotypes used from the Gediflux pane, their corresponding
 648 number, and year of release.

Cv.Number	Genotype name	Year of release
110	Bledor	1960
109	RUFUS	1950
108	Folke	1960
107	Starke II	1970
106	Cellule	2010
105	Midas	2000
104	Toronto	1950
103	CORINTHIAN	1940
102	Obelisk	1970
101	Tremie	2010
100	Caribo	1940
99	Recital	2000
98	Stava	1970
97	Beaver	1950
96	Premio	2010
95	Julius	2000
94	Rosario	2000
93	Champlein	1940
92	Valdor	2010
91	Walde	1970
90	Celesta	1940
89	Graham	2010
88	Professeur Marchal known as Prof Marshal	1960
87	Holme	1990
86	Ritmo	1970
85	Fidel	1960
84	Sideral	2000
83	Albatross	1950
82	Bergamo	2010
81	Stella	1990
80	Estica	1940
79	Capitole	1960
78	Arminda	1950
77	Biscay	1940
76	Eroica	1940
75	Expert	1990

74	Calumet	2010
73	Criewener 192	1940
72	Brons	2010
71	Zemon	1970
70	TARAS	1950
69	Cadenza	1960
68	Virtus	1950
67	Talent	1970
66	Paragon	2000
65	MIKON	1940
64	Manager	2000
63	Renan	1970
62	Florian	1940
61	Urban	1950
60	RECORD	1950
59	MIRAS	1950
58	Warrior	1970
57	Pontus	1950
56	Elite Lepeuple	1960
55	Soissons	1980
54	Almus	1940
53	Etoile de Choisy	1960
52	Atlass	2010
51	Edgar	2010
50	Aztec	1940
49	Moulin	1950
48	Granada	1940
47	Claire	1940
46	Paindor	1990
45	Galactic	2000
44	Reflection	2010
43	Kanzler	1940
42	Ceylon	2010
41	Danubius	1940
40	Courtot	2000
39	Tobak	2010
38	Dekan	2000
37	Apache	2000
36	Apollo	2000
35	Hardi	1960
34	Parador	2000
33	Norda	
32	Centenaire	2010
31	Prima	1950
30	MINA	1950
29	Kranich	1960
28	MARCO	1940
27	Haven	1960

26	Minister	1950
25	Arina	2000
24	Sterling	1990
23	Festival	1980
22	Barok	2000
21	Tommi	2000
20	Vilmorin 53	1940
19	Maris Huntsman	1960
18	Pajero	2000
17	Boisseau	2010
16	Kadolzer	1940
15	Beaufort	1950
14	Leda	1960
13	Orestis	1970
12	Antonius	2000
11	Capitaine	1960
10	Pernel	1970
9	CYRANO	1940
8	Cama	1960
7	Cappelle Desprez	1950
6	Alba	1940
5	Odeon	1970
4	KWS Smart	
3	Gamin	1960
2	Thesee	1980
1	LG Apollo	